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Putting public services into enterprise system- Predicting employees' acceptance of transformational government technology in an expanded technology acceptance model

Abstract

This paper reports the findings of a study that investigated employees' acceptance of enterprise systems in public sector in Sri Lanka. Survey methodology was used and public sector employees, who fulfilled the sample selection criteria set for the study responded. To examine the hypothesized relationships structural equation modelling was performed and five separate models were tested. The best-fitting model suggests that ease of use has significant effect on behavioural intention to use enterprise systems. Of the contextual factors investigated, formal internal training had the single highest significant contribution. The findings provide understanding and insight into important aspects of technology acceptance by public sector employees. The findings imply the need of contextualising research models instead of applying generic models that were developed and tested outside of public sector. The findings will be of interest to stakeholders of public sector, academics, researchers and practitioners, world-wide.

Keywords: Enterprise systems, public sector, technology acceptance, training.

Introduction

Workplace and work have become more complex and time pressured requiring employees to have kaleidoscope thinking, view different angles and have an integrated perspective. In response, organisations increasingly dependent on technologies; evidence for technological transformations at work for process improvements are in abundance (see Pedersen, 2018). Among these technological transformations, organisations world-wide depicted their preference for enterprise systems (ES) to effectively manage the entire enterprise in an integrated manner. In this endeavour, public sector enterprises are not an exception (Pedersen, 2018; Pitchay et al., 2016). With the implementation of ES, public sector enterprises expect to realize aims of

transformational government (t-government) in value creation and the management of internal and external processes without constrained by time, space and/or physical conditions generally visible in the public sector (Pedersen, 2018).

However, previous studies provided evidence for the underutilization of ES in public sector enterprises, which could mainly be attributed to people-related factors (e.g., Rehouma and Hofmann, 2018). Although the benefits of the implementation of ES in public sector enterprises are well documented (see Pedersen, 2018; Pitchay et al., 2016), such benefits are difficult to be realized unless these systems are accepted and used by employees. In other words, any organisation's return on investment from information technology (IT)-based systems highly dependent on the willingness of employees to accept and use the system to its full potential (Davis, 1989). The literature suggests that the acceptance of any IT-based system can mainly be attributed to innovative work behaviour of employees (Elias et al., 2012; Peng, 2017). Employees in the public sector are observed to perceive more barriers that limit their innovative work behaviour and suffer from fear and anxiety of innovation and modernization at work than employees in the private sector (Rehouma and Hofmann, 2018). Although an abundance of research studies is available on the acceptance of IT-based systems by employees in the private sector, transferring these findings from the private sector to the public sector is not promising (Rehouma and Hofmann, 2018). Therefore, it is important to understand the conditions under which employees in the public sector accept any IT-based system. However, research studies on the acceptance of IT-based systems in the public sector mainly concentrate on either the government to citizen (G2C) perspective or the government to business (G2B) perspective (see Rehouma and Hofmann [2018] for a detailed review). There are very limited number of research studies (e.g., Holden et al., 2012; Pitchay et al., 2016) available in the main stream publications that investigated the acceptance of any IT-based system by employees in the public sector, which is the interaction between the government and its employees (G2E). Therefore, it is important to understand public sector employees' acceptance of ES for successful implementations since such systems play a vital role in realizing t-government expectations. Therefore, the main intention of our study is to contribute to fill this research gap in the literature. In doing so, we proposed a conceptual model and tested relationships between public sector employees' perceptions towards ES and its acceptance based on an expanded technology acceptance model (TAM).

In addition to the above mentioned main research gap, which our study aimed to address, it also makes two other important contributions to the theory and practice. First, user technology acceptance has not been well researched in the context of public sector in developing countries

(Marston et al., 2016). The literature describes the existence of global digital divide between developed and developing countries (Marston et al., 2016). Of the two perspectives of global digital divide, one describes the division in terms of ownership and access to technology such as personal computers and internet connection. The other describes technology acceptance by individuals (Marston et al., 2016). The primarily focus of research from developing country perspective has been on ownership and access to technology rather than technology acceptance (see Marston et al., 2016). We investigated the acceptance of ES by public sector employees in a developing country, i.e., Sri Lanka. The Government of Sri Lanka launched e-Sri Lanka project as a five-year national development initiative in 2005. Since then, several government-led programmes were introduced to move from *mere web presence* to *IT-based interaction to transaction to transformation* for efficient and faster delivery of services to its stakeholders. Therefore, as a sector that delivers important services to the nation and a provider of equal employment opportunities to its citizens, it is important to understand employees' acceptance of IT-based systems.

Second, the use of an enterprise system could be voluntary or mandatory. A limited number of studies empirically investigated the antecedents and consequences of mandatory adoption of technologies (e.g., Chan et al., 2010). For the reasons justified in the next section, the present study examined mandated adoption of ES in public sector by proposing a framework built on the four core constructs of TAM. Since TAM (Davis, 1989) was developed and has been primarily validated in the contexts of voluntary adoption, the applicability of these findings to mandatory contexts is not clear. In this regard, DeLone and McLean (2003) argue that system use is not simply dichotomous by stating "the rejection of 'system use' as a success variable when its usage is mandatory is flawed. Even when use is mandatory, variability in the quality and intensity of its use is likely to have a significant impact on the realization of the system benefits" (p.8). Previous studies such as Brown et al. (2002) suggest that relationships theorized and validated in voluntary contexts could be different to that of in mandatory contexts. For example, the relative contribution of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use in determining user acceptance in TAM may differ in mandatory adoption of technologies (see Brown et al., 2002; Venkatesh et al., 2003). Further, prior studies (e.g., Venkatesh and Bala, 2008) identify one of the ways of expanding generic theoretical models of technology acceptance is by examining the antecedents in different contexts. In the present study, we used the term *mandatory* since the decision to adopt ES in the public sector in our sample is determined by the policies of the government. Therefore, the modelling and validation of

antecedents in our study context could reveal determinants leading to the acceptance and effective use of ES contributing to the existing theory and practice.

Literature review

Perceptions towards enterprise systems and user acceptance

Enterprise systems, like enterprise resource planning (ERP), are identified as application software packages that promise the seamless integration of data flowing through an organisation (Davenport, 1998: p. 121). The implementation of ES may be viewed as a replacement of the existing business model rather than an upgrade of business processes and associated workflows (Sykes et al., 2014). Employees' acceptance of ES, therefore, can be identified as an individual innovation within an organisation (see Elias et al., 2012; Peng, 2017). Research has theorized and tested user perception of IT-based systems building on the arguments of the theory of reasoned action (TRA) (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975) and TAM (Davis, 1989). Technology acceptance model has been expanded over time to TAM 2, TAM 3, and unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT). Still, TAM remains as the most widely-used theorization, which has also been supported through validations, applications and replications encompassing various technologies such as word processing, spreadsheets, e-mail, internet, mobile computing devices, electronic commerce and mobile apps (see Rondan-Cataluña et al., 2015). Since TAM is not developed for the specific context of public sector enterprises, and a limited number of studies have been conducted on the employees' acceptance of any IT-based system in the public sector, we believe that if TAM is used in its generic form, it may not fully capture characteristics of public sector employees. Although we propose a framework that includes the core constructs of TAM, we extended TAM for the inclusion of individual, job-level and context-related characteristics. Three individual characteristics included in the investigation were age, gender and the highest level of education. The job-level characteristic included was job rank. In addition, we included one context-related characteristic named "formal training on ES" to capture the receipt of formal training by employees to facilitate the use of ES. The main reason for this inclusion is that the literature (see Marston et al., 2016) on the global digital divide suggests that the lack of skills in employees hinder the use of IT-based systems in developing countries. Therefore, building on the core constructs in TAM as a convincing framework and by extending the same, we seek to predict and explain public sector employees' rational for the acceptance of ES. The conceptual model developed for the study is shown in Figure 1. In the sections to follow, the relevant literature is reviewed and hypotheses are proposed.

Figure 1 about here

Behavioural intention to use

The theory of reasoned action suggests that behavioural intention is the single best immediate predictor of the actual behaviour (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). Hence, an individual's behavioural intention to conduct or not to conduct a particular action is inseparable from conducting the action. Technology acceptance model also conveys that behavioural intention to use a given system captures technology acceptance since it is the single best predictor of the actual use of the system (Davis, 1989). If motivational factors behind behavioural intention can be captured, these can be interpreted as the factors that predict the actual action. In the present study, we intended to identify motivational factors that predict behavioural intention to use ES in public sector enterprises. Building on TAM (Davis, 1989), we also propose that the ease of use, perceived usefulness and attitude to use (as shown in figure 1 and detailed in the below subsections) predict behavioural intention to use a particular enterprise system.

Attitude to use

Behavioural intention to use is predicted by an individual's attitude towards the usage (Davis, 1989). Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) identified attitude to use as a positive feeling in conducting the intended behaviour. Davis (1989, 1993) showed the decisiveness of attitude to use on behavioural intention to use a given technology. Over the years, research empirically supported this relationship (such as Alharbi and Drew, 2014; Joo and Choi, 2015; Yoon, 2016). In the present study, the term attitude to use is defined as the degree of positive feelings in using ES in the public sector, and it is hypothesised:

H1: Attitude to use has a positive effect on behavioural intention to use a particular enterprise system

Perceived usefulness

Attitude to use is theorized and empirically validated as determined by perceived usefulness, where perceived usefulness is the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system would improve his/her task performance (see Davis, 1989, 1993). The literature supports (see Rondan-Cataluña et al., 2015) for a positive relationship between perceived usefulness and attitude to use. In the present study, perceived usefulness is defined as the degree to which an

employee believes that using a particular enterprise system would improve task performance. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H2: Perceived usefulness has a positive effect on attitude to use a particular enterprise system

When H1 and H2 are taken together (as shown in Figure 1), it is predicted that attitude to use mediates between perceived usefulness and behavioural intention to use. Although TAM in its generic form proposed a complete mediation by attitude to use, subsequent TAM research identified attitude to use as a partial mediator (see Davis et al., 1989: pp. 995–996; Davis and Venkatesh, 1996). This situation is interpreted as individuals may intend to use a particular system even without a positive attitude if they perceive the system would improve task performance. Previous studies such as Yoon (2016) and Venkatesh and Bala (2008) also support a direct positive relationship between perceived usefulness and behavioural intention to use. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H3: Perceived usefulness has a positive effect on behavioural intention to use a particular enterprise system

Perceived ease of use

Perceived usefulness is theorized and empirically validated as determined by perceived ease of use, where perceived ease of use is the “degree to which an individual believes that using a particular system would be free of effort” (Davis, 1989, p. 195). Previous studies such as Yoon (2016), Joo and Choi (2015) and Davis (1989) provided support for a positive relationship between perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. In the present study, perceived ease of use is defined as the degree to which an employee believes that using a particular enterprise system would be free of effort, and it is hypothesised:

H4: Perceived ease of use has a positive effect on perceived usefulness of a particular enterprise system

When H3 and H4 are taken together (as shown in Figure 1), it is predicted that perceived usefulness mediates the relationship between ease of use and behavioural intention. Previous studies such as Davis (1989) and Rondan-Cataluña et al. (2015) also provided evidence for a positive relationship between perceived ease of use and attitude to use. These studies suggest that when a system is perceived to be easy to use, users develop a positive attitude towards the use. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H5: Perceived ease of use has a positive effect on attitude to use a particular enterprise system

When H1 and H5 are taken together (as shown in Figure 1), it is predicted that attitude to use mediates the relationship between ease of use and behavioural intention. When H1, H2, and H4 are taken together, it is predicted that both perceived usefulness and attitude to use mediate the relationship between ease of use and behavioural intention. Previous research such as Yoon (2016), Joo and Choi (2015) and Davis (1989) provided support for this relationship. Further, previous research such as Yoon (2016), Alharbi and Drew (2014) and Venkatesh and Bala (2008) provided empirical support for the direct relationship between perceived ease of use and behavioural intention to use. Therefore, it is also hypothesised:

H6: Perceived ease of use has a positive effect on behavioural intention to use a particular enterprise system

Age

Building on the fact that developing countries are late in the implementation of ES in the public sector and the prevalence of an increasingly aging labour force in the sector, it is important to understand the ways in which age relates to perceptions towards ES. In this regard, Howe and Strauss (2000, p.43) argue that individuals' behavioural tendencies can be tracked by birth cohort; a clear distinction is visible between individuals born in and after 1982 and those born before. The literature also suggests that employees older than 40 years of age are typically identified as being less willing to adapt to changes at work and accept new technologies (Dogruel et al., 2015; Elias et al., 2012). Younger adults found to perceive lower levels of computer and Internet anxiety than their older counterparts, who become confronted with such technologies in a later stage of their lives (Elias et al., 2012; Tarhini et al., 2014); younger adults found to incur few concerns when appropriating computer technologies for their work (Dogruel et al., 2015). Building on these previous studies, it is hypothesised:

H7a. Younger employees may perceive a higher level of ease of use of a particular enterprise system

H7b. Younger employees may perceive a higher level of usefulness of a particular enterprise system

Sex

The literature suggests that sex plays an important role in technology acceptance, where men and woman are different in their perceptions towards the ease of use and usefulness of ES (Tarhini et al., 2014; Terzis and Economides, 2011; Venkatesh et al., 2003). For instance, Venkatesh et al. (2003) report that the effect of sex was significant on perceived usefulness, where the effect on men is stronger with compared to women. The literature also supports the contention that men place higher importance on usefulness with compared to women (Terzis and Economides, 2011). Building on these previous studies, it is hypothesised:

- H8a. Female employees may perceive a higher level of ease of use of a particular enterprise system
- H8b. Male employees may perceive a higher level of usefulness of a particular enterprise system

The level of formal education

The literature suggests the importance of level of formal education in the acceptance of new technologies (Elias et al., 2012; Peltier et al., 2012). It is suggested that more educated individuals have a greater exposure to new ideas, better understanding of technological products (e.g., computers), and they may find less switching costs associated with new technologies (Peltier et al., 2012). Building on these previous studies, it is hypothesised:

- H9a. Employees with more years of formal education may perceive a higher level of ease of use of a particular enterprise system.
- H9b. Employees with more years of formal education may perceive a higher level of usefulness of a particular enterprise system

Formal internal training on ES

The possession of skills related to information and communication technologies support employees to perform a variety of tasks that demand multiple skills and more non-routine cognitive tasks (Peng, 2017). Organisations experience the need of providing either training or retraining for employees to keep up with job demands when various forms of technologies are adopted in the workplace (Elias et al., 2012). Information systems related instruction received by users through formal internal sources provide better understanding and create more favourable attitude towards any system (Holden et al., 2012). In the specific context of IT-based systems, formal internal training operates as a salient characteristic that effect both perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness (Holden et al., 2012). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H10a. Employees with formal internal training on ES may perceive a higher level of ease of use of a particular enterprise system

H10b. Employees with formal internal training on ES may perceive a higher level of usefulness of a particular enterprise system

Job rank

Previous research such as Wickramasinghe and Karunasekara (2012) reveals significant differences between executive and non-executive users in their perceptions towards the performance and post-implementation impact on the use of IT-based systems. For example, Wickramasinghe and Karunasekara (2012) found significant differences between executive and non-executive users in their perceptions towards the performance and post-implementation impact on the use of information systems. Building on these arguments, we propose that individuals in executive job ranks may perceive higher levels of perceived ease of use and usefulness than individuals in non-executive ranks. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H11a. Employees in executive job rank may perceive a higher level of ease of use of a particular enterprise system

H11b. Employees in executive job rank may perceive a higher level of usefulness of a particular enterprise system

Method

Sample of the study and method of data collection

We selected a convenience sample of 250 employees engaged in public sector enterprises that implemented ES, where these were in operation covering the entire enterprise for over three years and the adoption was mandatory. We excluded employees in the job categories of IT-producing jobs. To ease the data collection, a contact person was identified from each enterprise. The questionnaire was in the English language, which is considered as a national language of the country. The questionnaire was pre-tested prior to the distribution. Further, the anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension. Of the 250 respondents, 56% were below 40 years of age; 44% had Bachelor's degree qualification; 87% were in non-executive job ranks; 61% were females, and 69% had formal internal training on ES. The population characteristics described in the Department of Census and Statistics (2018, p. 84) are reflected in our sample characteristics.

Measurement scales

The main constructs of usefulness, ease of use, attitude to use and behavioural intention were operationalized using the standard scales of Davis, et al. (1989) and Davis and Venkatesh (1996). The seven-point Likert type scale used ranged from 7 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree) as suggested by Davis and Venkatesh (1996). As detailed in the section on the *methods of data analysis*, the validity and reliability of the scales were tested and the results are given in Appendix 1 to 4. In addition, age, sex, the highest level of education, job rank and formal internal training on ES were included to identify attributes of the respondents. Sex was coded as 0 (female) and 1 (male); age was coded as 1 (below 40 years of age) and 0 (above 40 years of age); the highest level of education was coded as 1 (with Bachelor's degree) and 0 (without Bachelor's degree); job rank was coded as 1 (executive) and 0 (non-executive). Formal internal training on ES was measured using a dichotomous (yes/no) question, where responses were coded as 1 (yes) and 0 (no).

Methods of data analyses

Variables were tested for common method variance using Harman's single-factor test, and yielded satisfactory results (for the procedure and thresholds, see Hair et al., 2006). Principal component factor analysis with varimax rotation was performed. Convergent validity was measured by average variance extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity was measured by the square root of AVE. Table 1 provides the results of the fit-indices. Appendix 1 to 4 provide the results of factor analysis of each construct. The results of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were assessed based on normed chi-square statistic (χ^2/df) and fit indices of Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), comparative fit index (CFI) and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) (for thresholds, see Arbuckle, 2007; Blunch, 2008). Independent sample t-test was used to test H7 to H11. Hedges' *g* statistic was computed to evaluate the effect size or the magnitude of the effect weighted as per the relative size of category (e.g., males versus females). Multiple regression was used to identify the contribution of each variable for the final model.

Results

Table 1 shows the results of factor analysis, summarizing the detailed results shown in Appendix 1 to 4. Table 2 shows descriptive statistics and inter-correlations of the variables. Table 3 shows the results of CFA conducted to examine hypothesized relationships. Model 1 did not achieve a satisfactory level of fit. Path coefficients of Model 1 did not support H3, H8a, H7b, H8b, H9b, H10b, and H11b. These non-significant paths were removed and ran Model 2.

Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 about here

As shown in Table 3, Model 2 achieved a satisfactory level of fit. Figure 2 shows Model 2 with path coefficients. As shown in Figure 2, H1 (0.673, $p < 0.001$), H2 (0.493, $p < 0.01$), H4 (0.655, $p < 0.001$), H5 (0.486, $p < 0.01$) and H6 (0.798, $p < 0.001$) were supported. Further, when H1 and H2 are taken together (as shown in Figure 2), the results support that attitude to use mediates between usefulness and behavioural intention to use. When H3 and H4 are taken together, the results support that usefulness mediates the relationship between ease of use and behavioural intention. When H1 and H5 are taken together, the results support that attitude to use mediates the relationship between ease of use and behavioural intention. When H1, H2, and H4 are taken together, the results support that both usefulness and attitude to use mediate the relationship between ease of use and behavioural intention.

With regard to contextual factors, age (0.152, $p < 0.001$), the highest level of education (0.235, $p < 0.001$), formal internal training on ES (0.294, $p < 0.001$) and job rank (0.124, $p < 0.001$) significantly positively predict ease of use. Figure 2 also shows the values of coefficient of determination. The coefficient of determination of 0.676 suggests that ease of use, usefulness, attitude to use, age, education, training, and job rank account for 68% of the variation of behavioural intention.

Figure 2 about here

In order to isolate the best-fitting model, we also ran Model 3, Model 4 and Model 5. As shown in Table 3, Model 5 achieved the best-fit with compared to all the models tested. Figure 3 shows Model 5 with path coefficients. As shown in Figure 3, standardized regression coefficient of 0.765 ($p < 0.001$) reveals that ease of use significantly positively predicts behavioural intention. Age (0.156, $p < 0.001$), the highest level of education (0.236, $p < 0.001$), formal internal training on ES (0.298, $p < 0.001$) and job rank (0.125, $p < 0.001$) significantly positively predict ease of use. The coefficient of determination of 0.642 suggests that ease of use, age, education, training and job rank account for 64% of the variation of behavioural intention.

Figure 3 about here

Table 4 shows that individuals below 40 years (mean = 3.23) perceive a significantly higher level of ease of use, supporting H7a. Individuals with Bachelor's degrees (3.45) perceive a significantly higher level of ease of use. This supports H9a. Individuals who had formal internal training (3.26) perceive a significantly higher level of ease of use, supporting H10a. Individuals in executive job ranks (3.53) perceive a significantly higher level of ease of use. This supports H11a. The effect size of .773 suggests that formal internal training had the largest effect on ease of use. The contribution of each contextual variable to the final model (Model 5) was analysed using multiple regression. As shown in Table 5, the combined contribution of all four contextual variables accounted for the highest adjusted R^2 of .243, and formal internal training had the highest single effect with R^2 change of .082.

Table 4 and Table 5 about here

Discussion of findings in relation to contributions to theory and implications for practice

Contributions of the findings for existing literature

Successful technological transformations in public sector enterprises is dependent on many factors, of which people related factors can be identified as one of the main deciding criteria that make enterprises more strategic, efficient and citizen centric. Research into technological implementations are important even in environments that mandate the adoption. We investigated the perceptions of public sector employees to explain their behavioural intention to use, which is an antecedent to the behaviour - actual use of ES. This study proposed and tested a conceptual model that was built on TAM. Although TAM is widely used in the literature to test the use of different technologies, and shown to be fit to explain the context of public sector enterprises, it is not specifically designed in or for the context of public sector enterprises, or mandatory contexts, or for developing countries. Hence, the use of TAM in its generic form may not capture specific contextual features. The incorporation of five contextual factors led to extend the relationships of the core constructs of TAM (Davis, 1989). These five factors represented individual (age, sex and the highest level of education), job level (job rank), and context-related (formal internal training on ES) factors. Formal internal training on ES is associated with the global digital divide, i.e., whether employees have access to technology and whether they possess skills to use the technology. In the present study, formal internal training on ES was

used to determine employees' behavioural intention to use ES. Since a limited number of empirical research investigated employees' acceptance of technologies in public sector world-wide, the findings of the study have important contributions to the literature and implications for public sector enterprises, practitioners, personnel involved in public sector IT implementations and policymakers, world-wide.

We tested the model proposed in Figure 1, and the results suggested that one of the main paths, i.e., the path from usefulness to behavioural intention was not significant. The non-significance of this path suggests that employees in public sector do not perceive usefulness to be important to use the system. The implications of this finding are discussed in the latter part of this paragraph. Further, the findings suggest that sex does not predict the perceptions of ease of use, and all five characteristics do not predict the perceptions of usefulness. Model 2 yielded a satisfactory level of fit as presented and discussed in relation to Table 3. Model 2 supported many of the assumptions of TAM and explained 68% of the variation of behavioural intention. Model 2 and subsequent models of 3 and 4 had attitude to use as one of the main variables, and paths related to attitude to use (H1, H2, H4 and H5) remained statistically significant. When considering contributions to the theory of TAM, these findings support arguments reviewed earlier such as Davis (1989). Specifically, the results support the effect of attitude to use on behavioural intention to use, and the effect of perceived usefulness on attitude to use. Since perceived usefulness is based on the belief that ES use leads to beneficial outcomes, the findings suggest that when public sector employees believe that ES use improves task performance (usefulness), attitude to use increases. The findings also support the mediation of attitude to use on the relationship between usefulness and behavioural intention. That is usefulness increases positive attitudes to use, which in turn increases intention to use. However, the findings do not support the path from usefulness to behavioural intention, which is predicted in H3. The rejection of H3 implies that without having positive attitudes, public sector employees may not intend to use ES even though they perceive the system as useful. Further, our findings imply that the model is more powerful with *attitude to use* construct. This finding supports the arguments of Davis (1989), Alharbi and Drew (2014) and Yoon (2016) while contradicts with the arguments of Davis et al. (1989), Davis and Venkatesh (1996) and Tarhini et al. (2014). It should be noted that all these previous studies were not conducted on employees in the public sector. The findings also support the relationship between perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. When public sector employees believe that using ES is free of effort (ease of use), their perceived usefulness increases. This supports previous studies such as Davis (1989) and several others reviewed earlier in the literature. Overall, when paths related to H1, H2, and H4

are taken together (as shown in Figure 2), the findings support that both perceived usefulness and attitude to use mediate the relationship between ease of use and behavioural intention. In other words, this indicates that when public sector employees perceive that ES is easy to use, they may consider ES to be useful, and in turn develop attitude to use, which ultimately creates positive feelings to perform the intended behaviour. i.e, actual use. This finding supports previous studies such as Davis (1989) and Yoon (2016). The results also support the direct relationship between perceived ease of use and attitude to use. This finding suggests that when ES is perceived to be easy to use, employees develop positive attitudes towards the use. Overall, the findings imply that attitude to use mediates the relationship between ease of use and behavioural intention, supporting previous studies such as Davis (1989) and Yoon (2016). The findings of the study also support the direct relationship between perceived ease of use and behavioural intention to use. This suggests that when ES is perceived to be easy to use, public sector employees develop an intention to use ES. This finding supports previous studies such as Yoon (2016) and Venkatesh and Bala (2008).

Without limiting our analysis to Model 2, we tested three alternative models, i.e., Models 3, 4, and 5, and identified Model 5 shown in Figure 3 as the best fitting model. It explained 64% of the variation of behavioural intention. Even though there is 4% reduction (68% - 64%), in the variation explained with compared to Model 2, we are inclined to accept Model 5 as the best-fitting model in terms of the fulfilment of fit indices. Model 5 suggests that the perceived ease of use is the critical factor for behavioural intention of employees in public sector enterprises. Further, perceived usefulness and attitude to use are not essential to develop a feeling to perform the intended behaviour. This situation can be explained as public sector employees intend to use the system if it is considered to be free of effort (ease of use) without perceiving that the use would improve their task performance (usefulness) and without developing positive feelings of using the system (attitude to use). We feel that this situation better describes the perception of employees in the public sector enterprises. Further, each of the four contextual factors had significant effect on behavioural intention via their influence on perceived ease of use. As shown in Tables 4 and 5, formal internal training had the most significant effect followed by education; the age of employees had the least contribution.

Overall, we discussed our findings in the above paragraphs in relation to contribution to the literature in the context of public sector enterprises. Although our study was confined to Sri Lanka, the theoretical contributions discussed in the above paragraphs have wide applicability. Further, our findings support the arguments made by Holden et al. (2012) and many others for the need of contextualizing technology acceptance models to suit the specific context (e.g.

public sector) instead of applying generic models or theories developed outside of the specific context. We identify this as one of the key contributions of our study to the literature, especially for public sector enterprises world-wide.

Implications of the findings for practice

An investigation on ES acceptance in public sector enterprises should not be solely for the pursuit of theoretical contributions. We have not found previous empirical studies that investigated employees' perceptions on the use of ES in public sector enterprises, in any country context. We empirically validated a framework that extended the relationships of core constructs of TAM for public sector enterprises to understand public sector employees' acceptance of ES. Although decisions to implement new technologies come at a higher level, such as the Ministry level, it is employees' acceptance of the technology that illustrates a successful implementation. Governments and employees in public sector enterprises frequently find technology-led organisation change efforts as a major challenge. Our study highlighted factors that should be taken into consideration to get employees' acceptance.

All actors involved in ES implementations in public sector such as key decision makers, managers of public sector enterprises, technical staff and all other employee users have different roles and expectations in designing and implementing ES. Therefore, although our study was conducted in Sri Lanka, our findings have important implications for practice, especially for public sector enterprises world-wide. First, the results imply the need of paying more attention to ease of use when designing ES. In other words, human computer interfaces should be designed cautiously for employees in public sector enterprises for them to perceive systems are easy to use. In doing so, public sector enterprises could contextualize target employees of public sector and the purposes of using ES to elucidate aspects that shape ease of use. Second, in connection to the above, the study paved the way to understand four contextual factors which should be taken into consideration due to their direct effect on ease of use. Third, similar to some previous studies such as Elias et al. (2012), we also identified the effect of age of users as an important factor in technology adoption in our context. The argument behind this reasoning is that computers were introduced in recent decades compared to the developed counterparts in the West, and advanced technologies, like ES in our study, were introduced even more recently. Therefore, the age of users may become a vital predictor of ease of use. Fourth, although we identified the age as one of the significant predictors, its contribution on ease of use is at the lowest with compared to other three predictors, namely, formal internal training on ES, education and job rank. Since the implementations of ES happen in the present day, age and the

level of education of employees are difficult to be changed. However, formal internal training on ES, as the most contributing contextual factor, could be used to prepare employees for the acceptance of enterprise systems in the public sector.

Conclusion

The purpose of our research was to investigate factors that affect acceptance of ES by employees in public sector enterprises. This paper detailed how we have extended the relationships of core constructs of TAM to propose our conceptual model for public sector enterprises. The analysis of five structural models led to understand how employees in public sector come to accept ES; the best-fitting model (Model 5) elucidated the most contributing factors that promote the acceptance of ES. The results imply the importance of ease of use, formal training on ES, the level of education, job rank and age as the determinants of employees' behavioural intention to use ES. Further, our results demonstrate that behavioural intention is more likely to be affected by employees' beliefs of ease of use rather than usefulness or attitude to use. Overall, our study enhanced the understanding of factors that influence the use of ES among employees in public sector enterprises under mandatory conditions. As discussed in detail in the above sections, our findings have important contributions to the existing literature as well as implications for practice.

Limitations and future research

First, we used the core constructs of TAM in our research model. Future research could consider other alternative models or a combination depending on their contexts. Second, we extended the relationships by the inclusion of five contextual factors. Future research could consider other external variables such as personal controllability. Third, our sample confined to a convenience sample of 250 employees. Although we are satisfied with the sample, it is more appealing to the academic community if other sampling methods, such as stratified random sampling, were used. Fourth, our research context is mandatory, and considered behavioural intention as a better predictor than intensity of use. However, future research could assess the possibility of incorporating variables such as user satisfaction as an indicator of acceptance; accordingly, a suitable theoretical framework should be selected to model user acceptance. In addition to above mentioned areas of research in connection to the limitations of the study, the findings pave the way to identify new areas of research on technology acceptance. For example, our research is not confined to one particular enterprise system. Our sample consisted of employees experiencing different types of ES, some are designed locally while some others are of foreign

origin with local customizations. It is accepted that technologies undergo different trajectories when applied outside of their context of production. Since technologies embody society and culture-related meanings and intersect with development theories, employee-related constructs that reflect the context of the study could be incorporated.

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Figure 1. Hypothesised model

Figure 2. Statistical diagram with standardized path coefficients after removing non-significant paths
 *** $p < .001$; ** $p < .01$

Figure 3. Statistical diagram with standardized path coefficients for best-fitting model as per goodness of fit criteria
 *** $p < .001$

Tables

Table 1 - Fit-indices - Principle component factor analysis

Variable	Explained variation	Cronbach's alpha	AVE	Construct reliability	Source of the measure
Ease of use	81.42	.962	.845	.970	Davis (1989)
Usefulness	86.51	.968	.865	.975	Davis (1989)
Attitude to use	91.13	.951	.879	.973	Davis (1989)
Behavioural intention	92.38	.917	.924	.960	Davis and Venkatesh (1996)

Table 2. Correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1 Age [†]	-	-	-							
2 Education [†]	-	-	-.188**	-						
3 Job rank [†]	-	-	.146*	.357**	-					
4 Training [†]	-	-	-.085	.089	.097	-				
5 Ease of use	3.77	.85	-.214**	.320**	.207**	.335**	.90			
6 Usefulness	3.69	.91	-.148*	.291**	.204**	.330**	.533**	.93		
7 Attitude to use	3.53	.94	-.101	.311**	.236**	.337**	.468**	.529**	.95	
8 Behavioural intention	3.73	.98	-.099	.260**	.209**	.290**	.628**	.237**	.559**	.96

Note: [†] Constructs are on dichotomous scales; diagonal entries, square root of AVE; off-diagonal entries, correlations between constructs; ** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$

Table 3. Results of model comparisons

Model	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
1 Hypothesised full model – all paths (Figure 1)	2.311	.957	.946	.311
2 Model after removing non-significant paths (Figure 2)	2.255	.959	.948	.071
3 Contextual factors-> Ease of use-> Usefulness-> Attitude to use-> Behavioural intention	2.191	.959	.946	.069
4 Contextual factors-> Ease of use-> Attitude to use -> Behavioural intention	2.137	.970	.958	.067
5 Contextual factors-> Ease of use-> Behavioural intention (Figure 3)	1.742	.983	.973	.054

Table 4. Ease of use - independent sample t-test

	Characteristic	Mean	SD	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Effect size
Age	Above 40 yrs	2.86	.81	-3.450	.001	.447
	Below 40 yrs	3.23	.85			
Education	Without Bachelors	2.88	.87	-5.820	.000	.710
	With Bachelors	3.45	.65			
Job rank	Non-Executive	3.00	.83	-3.336	.001	.635
	Executive	3.53	.86			
Training	No	2.64	.87	-5.339	.000	.773
	Yes	3.26	.77			

Table 5. Summarized results - regression analysis

Model	Characteristic	β	R ²	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics		
					R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change
1	Age	.214**	.046	.042	.046	10.902	.001
2	Age	.159**	.127	.120	.081	22.958	.000
	Education	.290***					
3	Age	.193**	.167	.156	.040	15.631	.001
	Education	.229**					
	Job rank	.194*					
4	Age	.167**	.249	.243	.082	26.063	.000
	Education	.218**					
	Job rank	.176*					
	Training	.289***					

* p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001.

Appendixes

Appendix 1. Ease of use

Item	Ease of use
Learning to operate ES would be easy for me	.933
It would be easy for me to become skillful at using ES	.932
My interaction with ES would be clear and understandable	.921
I would find it easy to get ES to do what I want it to do	.920
I would find ES to be flexible to interact with	.910
I would find ES easy to use	.900
Explained variation	81.42
Cronbach's alpha	.962
AVE	.845
Construct reliability	.970

Appendix 2. Usefulness

Item	Usefulness
Using ES would make it easier to do my job	.957
Using ES in my job would increase my productivity	.953
Using ES would enhance my effectiveness on the job	.948
Using ES would improve my job performance	.941
I would find ES useful in my job	.934
Using ES in my job would enable me to accomplish tasks more quickly	.843
Explained variation	86.51
Cronbach's alpha	.968
AVE	.865
Construct reliability	.975

Appendix 3. Attitude to use

Item	Attitude to use
I like the idea of using ES	.971
Using ES provided me with a lot of enjoyment	.957
I believe it is a good idea to use ES for my work	.936
I have a generally favourable attitude toward using ES	.915
Overall, I enjoyed using ES	.908
Explained variation	91.13
Cronbach's alpha	.951
AVE	.879
Construct reliability	.973

Appendix 4. Behavioural intention

Item	Behavioural intention
Given that I had access to ES, I predict that I would use it	.961
Assuming I had access to ES, I intend to use it	.961
Explained variation	92.38
Cronbach's alpha	.917
AVE	.924
Construct reliability	.960